

A Note on a New Method of Volumetric Estimation of Mercuric Oxide.

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Mercuric oxide completely dissolves in sodium thiosulphate solution in the cold with liberation of an equivalent amount of alkali and formation of the complex mercury sodium thiosulphate. The reaction is a quantitative one and the amount of mercuric oxide in a sample can be easily determined by titrating the alkali disengaged. The excess of thiosulphate present does not interfere with the titration of the alkali. This furnishes a rapid method of evaluating mercuric oxide in commercial samples of the same, in basic salts of mercury and in various medicinal preparations. It has got sure advantages over the potassium iodide method of Rupp and Schirmer (*Pharm. Zeit.*, 1908, 53, 928) being much less expensive ; the results are however equally good. The reaction involved is represented by the following equation :—

EXPERIMENTAL.

At first a known amount of alkali was taken mixed with different quantities of sodium thiosulphate solution and titrated with standard acid. The results are tabulated below :—

Alkali taken.	N/5 Thiosulphate added.	Acid required.
25 c.c.	0 c.c.	25·25 c.c.
..	0 ..	25·25 ..
..	10 ..	25·25 ..
..	20 ..	25·25 ..
..	30 ..	25·3 ..
..	40 ..	25·3 ..

The results indicate that the presence of thiosulphate has no effect on the alkali titration.

To determine the strength of the mercuric oxide a weighed amount of the substance was taken and estimated by the potassium iodide method. Thus a weighed amount of mercuric oxide was dissolved in excess of potassium iodide solution and the liberated caustic soda was titrated with N/10 sulphuric acid ($f=0.9700$). Results are given below.

HgO taken.	Acid required.	Hg found.	Percentage.
2109 gms.	20.25 c.c.	19642 gms.	93.1
2673 ,,	25.6 ,,	24882 ,,	92.9

A weighed amount of mercuric oxide was taken in each case. This was dissolved in the cold in excess of thiosulphate solution and the liberated caustic soda as titrated with N/10 sulphuric acid. In each case the total volume of the solution was maintained at or about 150 c.c. with varying amounts of thiosulphate, the results of which are tabulated below:—

TABLE I.

NaOH titrated with N/10 sulphuric acid ($f=0.9700$).

HgO taken.	Acid required.	Hg found.	Per cent.	Thiosulphate added.
0665 gms.	8.3 c.c.	08051 gms.	93.07	2 gms.
1958 ,,	18.6 ,,	18236 ,,	93.13	,,
2022 ,,	19.4 ,,	18818 ,,	93.2	,,
2094 ,,	21.1 ,,	19497 ,,	93.1	,,
3576 ,,	34.3 ,,	33281 ,,	93.09	,,
2388 ,,	22.0 ,,	22213 ,,	93.14	,,

TABLE II.

HgO taken.	Acid required.	Hg found.	Per cent.	Thiosulphate added.
2161 gms.	20.65 c.c.	20003 gms.	93.15	4 gms.
2759 ,,	26.5 ,,	25705 ,,	93.17	,,
2655 ,,	25.5 ,,	24735 ,,	93.16	,,
2943 ,,	28.25 ,,	27402 ,,	93.1	,,

TABLE III.

HgO taken.	Acid required.	Hg found.	Percentage.	Thiosulphate added.
·2606 gms.	25·1 c.c.	·24947 gms.	93·4	6 gms.
·1745 „	16·8 „	·16296 „	93·3	„
·1408 „	13·55 „	·131435 „	93·3	„

TABLE IV.

HgO taken.	Acid required.	Hg found.	Per cent.	Thiosulphate added.
·1238 gms.	11·9 c.c.	·11543 gms.	93·5	7·5 gms.
·2503 „	24·1 „	·23377 „	93·39	„
·3240 „	31·2 „	·30264 „	93·9	„

Pure mercuric oxide contains 93·06 per cent. of mercury.

It should be pointed out here that too much excess of thiosulphate makes the end point less sharp and renders the result a little high as shown in Table III and IV. The presence of too much excess of thiosulphate in the solution therefore should be carefully avoided.

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